

A Square Matrix Classification Scheme

Scaling/Diagonal Matrices

Scales different dimensions of a vector

```
A=[rand(), 0.0;  
 0.0, rand()];
```

```
showTransformation(A)
```

```
S = 2x2  
 1 0  
 0 1  
Lambda = 2x2  
 0.8147 0  
 0 0.9058
```

Warning: MATLAB has disabled some advanced graphics rendering features by switching to software OpenGL. For more information, [click here](#).

Special Case: Identity Matrix

Preserves everything - output vectors equal to input vectors

```
I=eye(2);  
showTransformation(I)
```

```
S = 2x2  
 1 0  
 0 1  
Lambda = 2x2  
 1 0  
 0 1
```


Special Case: Zero Matrix

Projects everything to the zero vector subspace - only outputs the zero vector

```
A=zeros(2);  
showTransformation(A)
```

```
S = 2x2  
 1  0  
 0  1  
Lambda = 2x2  
 0  0  
 0  0
```


Special Case: Mirror/Reflection Matrix

Swaps quadrants about - reflects vectors about a subspace

```
A=[-1,0;  
 0,1];  
showTransformation(A)
```

```
S = 2x2  
 1  0  
 0  1  
Lambda = 2x2  
-1  0  
 0  1
```


Special Case: Scalar Matrices

Scales vectors preserving direction/vectorspace aspect ratio

```
A=1.4*eye(2);  
showTransformation(A)
```

```
S = 2x2
    1    0
    0    1
Lambda = 2x2
    1.4000    0
    0    1.4000
```


Off-Diagonal Matrices

A shear matrix skews our cube/rectangular cuboid into a parallelepiped (or generalized parallelogram in higher dimensions). The determinant is the volume scaling factor of the parallelepiped:

```
A=[ 0.0, 0.2;
    -0.8, 0.0]+I;
showTransformation(A)
```

```
S = 2x2 complex
    0.0000 - 0.4472i    0.0000 + 0.4472i
    0.8944 + 0.0000i    0.8944 + 0.0000i
Lambda = 2x2 complex
    1.0000 + 0.4000i    0.0000 + 0.0000i
    0.0000 + 0.0000i    1.0000 - 0.4000i
```


Special Case: Orthogonal Matrices

Pure rotation - preserves vector magnitude and changes direction. These are special shear matrices which exchange dimensional components of input vectors to produce corresponding output vectors which are equal in size.

```
theta = pi / 4;
Q = [cos(theta), -sin(theta); sin(theta), cos(theta)];
showTransformation(Q)
```

```
S = 2x2 complex
    0.7071 + 0.0000i    0.7071 + 0.0000i
```

```

0.0000 - 0.7071i    0.0000 + 0.7071i
Lambda = 2x2 complex
0.7071 + 0.7071i    0.0000 + 0.0000i
0.0000 + 0.0000i    0.7071 - 0.7071i

```


Combinations/Decomposition

Any linear transformation is possible

```

A=rand(2);
showTransformation(A)

```

```

S = 2x2
0.6469    -0.6323
0.7626     0.7747
Lambda = 2x2
0.8724     0
0    -0.6479

```


Special Case: Projection Matrices

Matrices with non-linearly independent columns which map to a subspace

```

P=[ .25, 0.7;
    .5, 1.4];
showTransformation(P)

```

```

S = 2x2
-0.9417    -0.4472
0.3363    -0.8944
Lambda = 2x2
0     0
0    1.6500

```


Special Case: Hermitian Matrices

todo

3-D Test

```

% Define cube vertices
vertices = [
    0 0 0; % Vertex 1
    1 0 0; % Vertex 2
    1 1 0; % Vertex 3
    0 1 0; % Vertex 4
    0 0 1; % Vertex 5
    1 0 1; % Vertex 6
    1 1 1; % Vertex 7
    0 1 1 % Vertex 8
];

% Define cube faces
faces = [
    1 2 3 4; % Bottom
    5 6 7 8; % Top
    1 5 8 4; % Side 1
    2 6 7 3; % Side 2
    1 2 6 5; % Side 3
    4 3 7 8 % Side 4
];

% Define colors for each face
colors = [1 0 0; % Red
          0 1 0; % Green
          0 0 1; % Blue
          1 1 0; % Yellow
          1 0 1; % Magenta
          0 1 1]; % Cyan

% Plot the original cube
figure;
subplot(1, 2, 1);
hold on;
for i = 1:size(faces, 1)

```

```

    patch('Vertices', vertices, 'Faces', faces(i, :), ...
          'FaceColor', colors(i, :), 'FaceAlpha', 0.7);
end
axis equal;
title('Original Cube');
xlabel('X'); ylabel('Y'); zlabel('Z');
view(3);

% Define a 3x3 transformation matrix
A = [2 0 0;
     0 1 1;
     0.5 0.5 1]; % Example transformation matrix

% Apply the transformation
transformed_vertices = (A * vertices)';

% Plot the transformed cube
subplot(1, 2, 2);
hold on;
for i = 1:size(faces, 1)
    patch('Vertices', transformed_vertices, 'Faces', faces(i, :), ...
          'FaceColor', colors(i, :), 'FaceAlpha', 0.7);
end
axis equal;
title('Transformed Cube');
xlabel('X'); ylabel('Y'); zlabel('Z');
view(3);

```



```

function showTransformation(A)

    x = linspace(-10, 10, 30);
    y = linspace(-5, 5, 15);
    [x, y] = meshgrid(x, y);
    X = [x(:), y(:)]';

    Y=A*X;

    [S Lambda]=eig(A)

    colors = zeros(size(X, 2), 3); % RGB color matrix
    for i = 1:size(X, 2)
        if X(1, i) > 0 && X(2, i) > 0
            colors(i, :) = [1, 0, 0]; % Red (Quadrant I)
        elseif X(1, i) < 0 && X(2, i) > 0
            colors(i, :) = [0, 0, 1]; % Blue (Quadrant II)
        elseif X(1, i) < 0 && X(2, i) < 0
            colors(i, :) = [0, 1, 0]; % Green (Quadrant III)
        elseif X(1, i) > 0 && X(2, i) < 0
            colors(i, :) = [1, 1, 0]; % Yellow (Quadrant IV)
        end
    end

    figure('Position', [50, 50, 400, 150]);
    hold on
    subplot(1, 2, 1)
    scatter(X(1, :), X(2, :), 50, colors, 'filled', 'MarkerFaceAlpha', 0.05);
    axis([-20 20 -20 20]); grid on;
    subplot(1, 2, 2)
    scatter(Y(1, :), Y(2, :), 50, colors, 'filled', 'MarkerFaceAlpha', 0.05);
    axis([-20 20 -20 20]); grid on;
    hold off;

end

```